

The Volatile and Mineralogy Mapping Orbiter (VMMO) Lunar Science Exploration Mission. R.V. Kruezelecky¹, I. Sinclair¹, A. Murzionak¹, Qi Yang Peng¹, D. Fermi¹, E. Cloutis², A. Cunje², K. Ryden³, C. Underwood³, C. Bridges³, N. Barasi³, A. Lucca Fabris³, S. Molina⁴, P. Rosa⁵, J. Rey⁴, R. Prata⁵, J-F Hamel⁶, M. Gameiro⁷, Y. Gao⁸, J. Madariaga⁹, Z. Martins¹⁰; ¹MPB Communications Inc. (MPBC) 147 Hymus Blvd., Pointe Claire, Québec, H9R 1E9, Canada, roman.kruezelecky@mpbc.ca; ²University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Ave. Winnipeg, Manitoba, R3B 2E9, Canada, e.cloutis@uwinnipeg.ca ; ³Surrey Space Centre, University of Surrey, Guildford, GU2 7XH, UK; ⁴Deimos Engineering and Systems SLU (DES), Calle Francia 9, Polígono Industrial La Nava III, 13500 Puertollano, Ciudad Real, Spain; ⁵Deimos Engenharia S.A. (DME), Av. Columbano Bordalo Pinheiro, No. 75, 9 A1 1070-061 Lisboa, Portugal; ⁶NGC Aerospace Ltd., 2995, Boul. Industriel, Sherbrooke, Québec, J1L 2T9 Canada; ⁷Critical Software, Parque Industrial de Taveiro, Lote 49, Coimbra, 3045-504, Portugal; ⁸King's College London, Strand Building, Strand, London, WC2R 2LS, UK; ⁹University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Bilbao, Spain; ¹⁰CQE, IMS and DEQ, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal.

Introduction: Sustained manned presence on the lunar surface requires access to usable quantities of relevant in-situ resources such as water-ice, oxygen, and suitable building materials. The NASA Lunar Crater Observation and Sensing Satellite (LCROSS) [1] lunar impactor experiment¹ found concentrations of water ice in ejecta from the south polar region Cabeus crater at the few percent level based on infrared spectral measurements of light reflected from the ejecta as it was illuminated by the Sun.

While the evidence for lunar water ice in permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) is compelling, major uncertainties exist in terms of its lateral extent and vertical distribution in the regolith, water-ice presence in significant surficial concentrations, and associated lunar diurnal water-ice cycle.

The spatial resolution of the spectral observations and imaging of the prior and planned relevant lunar missions is on the order of ~100 meters and greater. Given that future lunar landers or rovers destined for PSRs will likely have limited mobility, there is a need to improve the spatial resolution and accuracy of maps of water ice in the lunar PSRs to the scale of 10s of metres.

The Lunar Volatile and Mineralogy Mapping Orbiter (VMMO) [2] lunar 16U Cubesat potential mission was initially developed by MPBC through the ESA SysNova LUCE competition. As co-winner of the SysNova LUCE competition, there was a follow-on ESA CDF study, a Phase 0 Study with CSA, and a Phase A study with ESA. VMMO is designed to actively explore for the presence of surficial water ice in PSRs in the Moon's South Pole region at high spatial resolution during the lunar night (Active Mode), and to conduct mineral and in-situ resource mapping across the lunar surface during the lunar day (Passive Mode).

VMMO will also study the lunar surficial in-situ resource mapping, focusing on ilmenite (FeTiO₃), and the cis-lunar radiation environment and its effects on the weathering of the lunar surface.

VMMO Overview: VMMO comprises a low-cost, highly capable 16U Cubesat, the Lunar Volatiles and Mineralogy Mapper (LVMM) science payload, the Surrey CLAIRE Compact LunAr Ionizing Radiation Environment, and the Deimos G3Star_Moon GNSS receiver payload tailored for the allocated lunar GNSS frequencies to provide improved lunar data geolocation.

The preliminary VMMO operations over the main mission stages are summarized in Figure 1. The VMMO spacecraft is designed to be transported to the Moon within a 16U CubeSat deployer accommodated on a larger transport vehicle as part of a NASA CLPS mission or as part of an Ariane launch into a relevant weekly bound lunar injection orbit.

During this transport stage, the power connection between VMMO and the transport vehicle will allow the CubeSat battery to remain charged and it will also provide heater power to the spacecraft to ensure the units remain within their survival temperatures.

Figure 1: Artist's rendition of the VMMO Mission.

Deimos VMMO 16U Cubesat: The supporting 16U Cubesat platform will include Enpulsion dual ion thrusters, a cold-gas propulsion for maneuvering and detumbling, a 200 W DC-DC power subsystem with two deployable solar power wings and fixed body-mounted solar panels, a fault tolerant, redundant on-board computer (OBC), and S-band (to lunar Pathfinder/Moonlight), and X-Band (direct to Earth) RF communications.

MPBC VMMO LVMM Science Payload: To meet these scientific objectives, the VMMO spacecraft will fly the LVMM multi-wave chemical Lidar payload which is being designed and developed by MPB Communications Inc. A preliminary 3D CAD image of the LVMM payload can be seen in Figure 2. The payload itself weighs less than 7 kg and includes a 4 W 1064 nm to 532 nm SHG, a 20 W PM fiber-laser at 1064 nm, a 4W fiber laser at 1560 nm, a broadband multispectral receiver with 78 mm O.D. primary aperture operating near 300, 532, 690, 850, 1064, 1350, 1560 and 1650 nm using one PCO-Panda UV-enhanced CMOS imager and two 640CSX SWIR InGaAs imagers, one dedicated to 1064 nm and the other to 1350, 1560 and 1650 nm. It also contains a laser transmitter with beam expander, avionics including a Xiphus-developed Q8 micro-controller, laser drivers and DC-DC power.

Figure 2: 3-D preliminary model of the LVMM science payload.

For the active imaging mode (see Figure 3), once the spacecraft is below 80°S latitude in its orbit, the LVMM fiber lasers and imagers are powered on ready for data acquisition to commence. The active imaging mode will be used mainly during the lunar night for both the detection of water ice in the PSRs as well as for the detection of any night-time frosting outside of the PSR regions.

Figure 3; (a) Active measurement mode and (b) water-ice analysis using analogue water-ice/regolith reference samples and diffuse reflectance spectra.

For the passive imaging mode (see Figure 4), the spacecraft will be able to map in-situ resources such as ilmenite and mineralogy during the lunar day by detecting the solar radiation reflected from the

lunar surface. The primary focus is on locations that may be considered for future lunar bases.

Figure 4: (a) LVMM Passive measurement mode during the sunlit lunar day and (b) passive mode spectral bands superimposed on lunar-relevant mineralogy spectra.

Payload data downlink operations will be carried out at the apoapsis of the orbit, either via the Lunar Pathfinder spacecraft in S-band or direct to Earth using X-band.

Conclusions: The VMMO mission will focus on the acquisition of high-resolution Active (Lunar night and PSRs) and Passive (lunar day) multi-wavelength images of the lunar South Pole region using a suitable lunar frozen orbit (LFO) to minimize the orbit station-keeping requirements. The primary mission goal is to obtain high spatial resolution (10s of metres) information about strategic sites on the moon where there is evidence of condensed volatiles in sheltered cold traps, as well as mapping of the lunar surficial in-situ resources such as ilmenite (FeTiO_3). This data can address key unknowns about the distribution of relevant lunar volatiles and resources to provide guidance for potential future landed mission operations to reduce their risks.

The mission will also provide data on the cis-lunar radiation environment using the CLAIRE MuREM sensor suite to assist lunar surface studies and future potential manned mission planning.

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